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Abstract:

This deliverable aims at presenting the Gender Equality Plan (GEP) of the DAM4CO₂ project.

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Definitions, Acronyms and Abbreviations

EB	Executive Board
EC	European Commission
EIC	European Innovation Council
EISMEA	European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency
GA	Grant Agreement
WP	Work Package
PIC	Participant Identification Code
COO	Coordinator
BEN	Beneficiary
GEP	Gender equality plan
R&I	Research and Innovation

Document History

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Approval History

	Name Surname	Date of Approval
WP Leader	Alessio Fuoco	15/01/2024
Coordinator*	Alessio Fuoco	30/01/2024

*on behalf of the EB

Introduction

The **Gender Equality Plan** aims to support and promote actions and commitments inspired by the principle of equal opportunities in different sector, scientific, technical, institutional and research activities foreseeing the participation of all members of DAM4CO₂ project. This objective is achieved with a series of actions aimed at pursuing the promotion of diversity, the fight against gender discrimination, transparency during all the lifespan of DAM4CO₂.

Gender equality is a fundamental value of the European Union¹. Strengthening gender equality and gender mainstreaming within EU's key funding program for research and innovation (R&I) is a fundamental right and key principle of the European Pillar of Social Rights². It is also an essential condition for an innovative, competitive, and thriving European economy. In December 2020, the Council of the EU in its conclusions on the New European Research Area¹, called on the European Commission and Member States to adopt a renewed focus on gender equality and gender mainstreaming³, including through GEPs and the integration of the gender dimension in Research. The Gender Equality Plan of DAM4CO₂, **DAM4CO₂-GEP**, responds to the requirements of the European Commission's Strategy⁴ for Gender Equality, which includes **objectives** and **actions** to make significant progress towards a Gender-Equal Europe.

The goal is to improve the European research and innovation system, create gender-equal working environments, where all talents can thrive and better integrate the gender dimension in projects to improve research quality as well as the relevance to society of the knowledge, technologies and innovations produced.

The **DAM4CO₂-GEP**, following the guidelines of European Strategy for Gender Equality 2020-2025⁵, includes two complementary and transversal main key-actions:

- A. **Governance and monitoring** of the plan, aimed to create a structure for the management, implementation and quantification of the GEP impact;
- B. **Communication, training, awareness** on gender equality issues, with the scope to produce awareness of gender issues among all the staff involved in the DAM4CO₂ at all levels.

The complementary and transversal **key-actions** support and allow the **specific actions** clustered into five areas of intervention: *Gender equality balance in leadership and decision-making; Gender equality in recruitment and training of young researchers/students; Work-life balance; Integration of the gender dimension in research; Prevention and fight against discrimination, harassment, and mobbing; (Fig.1).*

Figure 1 Structure of the Gender Equality Plan. Relationship between key-actions and specific actions

Governance and Monitoring

The DAM4CO₂ project will establish a working group (GE-DAM4CO₂) for the creation of a gender balance within all the project activities. The GE-DAM4CO₂ will monitor and produce material for actions and communication at various levels in a broader perspective.

Objective	Action
O1. Appointment of an Equality manager that will be supported by a Gender-Equality team (GE-DAM4CO ₂)	Identification of figures responsible for monitoring and implementing gender actions and commitments.
O2. Systematic collection of DAM4CO ₂ data from a gender perspective	Creation of a Gender Data Folder (GDF) periodically fed with new data from the collection of the DAM4CO ₂ project related to the gender issues. The folder with the collation data will be created in the private section be linked to by the following website www.dam4co2.eu . Moreover, a public section of our website will be dedicated to the dissemination and communication of gender balance issues of the DAM4CO ₂ project.

Timeline

	2024		2025		2026	
O1	█					
O2	█	█	█	█	█	█

Awareness Raising and Communication

The cultural change on gender issues within the European Union can only occur through awareness and information on gender inequalities and the related impact on a personal and working level. For this reason, within the DAM4CO₂ project, a communication and awareness campaign will be carried out among both structured and unstructured staff as well as a broader audience on gender issues.

Objective	Action
O3. The aim is to raise awareness of gender issues and their impact on the scientific research of the DAM4CO ₂ project.	1. Creation of a page on the DAM4CO ₂ site which collects all the material relating to the gender balance (e.g. tasks, staff, events, publications). 2. Active promotion (through participation in events or as organizers) within the organization of awareness days e valorisation of differences, such as for example the <i>International Day of Women and Girls in Science</i> , <i>International Women in Engineering Day</i> and the <i>International Day against homophobia, biphobia and transphobia</i> .
O4. Conduct training and awareness-raising actions on discrimination, harassment and mobbing	1. Plan participation in events dedicated to training and raising awareness on discrimination, harassment and mobbing. 2. Raising awareness through the dissemination of messages by means of socials inspired by the principles of equal opportunities and the promotion of diversity

Timeline

	2024		2025		2026	
O3						
O4						

Gender Equality Balance in Leadership and Decision-Making

The first area on which the DAM4CO₂-GEP wants to intervene concerns gender equality in top management positions and in decision-making bodies, to directly address the inequalities that are often present at the top of organizations as well as in positions of responsibility for project.

Objective	Action
O5. Reduce gender inequality in positions of responsibility: working groups, management of special projects.	Ensure the appointment of important roles within the project (such as work package leader, communication leader, etc.) achieving the most balanced composition possible.
O6. Reduce gender inequality in positions of committees and commissions.	Appoint the commissions for recruitment and training of young researchers/students ensuring a gender equity.

Timeline

	2024		2025		2026	
O5	█	█				
O6	█	█	█	█	█	█

Gender equality in recruitment and training of young researchers/students

The DAM4CO₂-GEP undertakes to act on different levels for achieving gender equality in recruitment and training of young researchers/students: Promote gender equality in the initial stages of recruitment and career development; Support the participation in international events of young researchers/students. Integrating the gender dimension into educational activities, as well as public engagement, is also crucial for the proper training of the next generation of professionals⁶.

Objective	Action
O7. Promote gender equality in the recruitment.	The evaluation commissions in recruitment competitions, during the CV evaluation phases, will take into account the transversal skills acquired by favoring the participation of the less represented gender (in cases of equal merit, for example, the youngest candidate will be favored, or the less represented differently-abled, male/female gender or conational/foreigner), in compliance with national laws. Moreover, the following actions will be guarantee: - Monitor the number of female and male candidates in each recruitment/promotion round – Ensure gender balance in interview panels - Guard a gender-sensitive assessment - Explicitly pay attention to implicit bias and gendered language - Ensure that feedback is constructive, gender-neutral and unambiguous.
O8. Encourage participation in international events of young researchers/students	Part of the project resources will be dedicated to the encouragement and participation of young researchers/students in international events, such as conferences, short-term mobility at the premises of other project partners, guaranteeing the principle of equal opportunities.

Timeline

	2024		2025		2026	
O7						
O8						

Work-life balance

The Work-Life Balance area focuses on creating a more welcoming environment and reconciling the two main spheres of personal life, through access to innovative working methods⁷.

Objective	Action
O9. Creating a more welcoming and productive work environment.	Adoption of innovative working methodologies and techniques that favor a correct conciliation between work and private life, such as tele-working and remote-working, even facilitating the purchase of workstations and laptops for structured and non-structured personnel by means of DAM4CO ₂ funds.
O10. Incentive to come back to work after parental and/or care duties.	Facilitating the come-back to work after periods of suspension for parental leave, by means of actions for reducing if required the work time or by supporting the international mobility and activity of DAM4CO ₂ project staff with care duties (e.g. parenting) even favoring teleworking and online meetings.

Timeline

	2024		2025		2026	
O9						
O10						

Integration of the gender dimension in research

Integrate gender dimension into research means integrate gender analysis into all stages of the research cycle^{8,9}: in the definition of research questions and hypotheses, in the selection of research methods, during the running of research activities, and in the analysis and dissemination and communication of data to assure excellence and quality in outcomes. Looking at potential gender differences and at issues related to gender equality generates added value in terms of research excellence, rigor, reproducibility, and creativity.

Objective	Action
<p>O11. Integrate gender dimension into all stages of the research cycle</p>	<p>Stage1: Research questions and hypotheses Brainstorming meetings will be organized in order to evaluate different hypotheses coming from different kinds of people while maximizing creativity.</p> <p>Stage 2: Selection of research methods, during the running of research activities. Actions such as online meetings between the different partners to discuss ongoing research will be an opportunity for discussion to take into account the different ideas coming from people with different genders.</p> <p>Stage3: Analysis data The data will be analyzed on their impact under a gender dimension. It is well known that climate change is related to the gender inequality¹⁰. The innovation and research of the DAM4CO₂ project is proposed as a strategy for the resolution and mitigation of various problems related to climate change. For this reason, the results obtained in terms of innovation and research will also be analyzed from the point of view of how they can improve and mitigate these gender differences.</p> <p>Stage4: Dissemination and communication Promote balanced participation between genders in organized conferences and panels as well as giving leadership roles in decision-making bodies related to communication (e.g. portfolio communication manager).</p>

Timeline

	2024	2025	2026
O11			

Prevention and fight against discrimination, harassment, and mobbing

Gender-based violence is both a cause and a consequence of gender inequality. It is any type of violence based on someone’s gender from physical to emotional to financial to sexual violence. In DAM4CO2-GEP, all types of actions will be adopted for preventing and combating all types of gender violence.

Objective	Action
O12. Create an inclusive working environment	Implementation of a code of conduct for the prevention of harassment which includes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Pay attention to implicit bias and gendered language or body-language. -Guarantee gender-neutral and unambiguous feedback. - Promote equal opportunities in terms of recruitment, compensation, access to training, promotion, termination, or retirement. - No discrimination in employment on the basis of race, color, sex, religion, political opinion, national extraction, or social origin, which has the effect of nullifying or impairing equality of opportunity or treatment in employment or occupation.
O13. Raising awareness of the DAM4CO ₂ project staff and even of a wider public	Raising awareness through the dissemination of messages that respond to the principles of gender neutrality, promotion of diversity, the fight against gender discrimination, through the project's social profiles and the dedicated web site.

Timeline

	2024		2025		2026	
O12						
O13						

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Consortium of DAM4CO₂

Number	Role	Short Name	Legal Name	Country	PIC
1	COO	CNR	CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	IT	999979500
2	BEN	INSTM	CONSORZIO INTERUNIVERSITARIO NAZIONALE PER LA SCIENZA E TECNOLOGIA DEI MATERIALI	IT	999991237
3	BEN	UPV	UNIVERSITAT POLITECNICA DE VALENCIA	ES	999864846
4	BEN	PRIMALCHIT	PRIMALCHIT SOLUTIONS	ES	892236168
5	BEN	Me-Sep	ME-SEP SPOLKA Z OGRANICZONA ODPOWIEDZIALNOSCIA	PL	887256382
6	BEN	USwan	SWANSEA UNIVERSITY	UK	999862033
7	BEN	UEdin	THE UNIVERSITY OF EDINBURGH	UK	999974941

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